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Re-calculation of air kerma to dose equivalent conversion coefficients for mono-energetic photons

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ABSTRACT: This work presents new calculations of conversion coefficients (CCs) from total air kerma to dose equivalent quantities $H'(0.07)$, $H'(3)$, $H^*(10)$, $H_p(0.07)$, $H_p(3)$, and $H_p(10)$ for area and personal dosimetry for mono-energetic photons in the energy range from 2 keV to 50 MeV, assuming secondary charged particle equilibrium. Calculations using the MCNP Monte Carlo code were performed for a large number of photon energies with the aim to prevent errors resulting from possible improper interpolation between currently available sparsely spaced CC values, when an average CC value over a photon fluence spectrum needs to be determined. The CC values were compared with the values published in the ISO 4037-3:2019 standard. A very close agreement was achieved for the majority of CCs. Larger discrepancies were found for some CCs, often for low photon energies or large angles of radiation incidence, which were taken from older publications or when CC values were interpolated or extrapolated. Furthermore, some differences were found in the MeV energy range which are significant for dosimeter calibrations, e.g., the presented values of CC to $H^*(10)$ for the main photon energies of ^{137}Cs and ^{60}Co radionuclides are both lower by 2.8 %. Finally, it was found that the values of CCs to $H_p(0.07; E, \alpha)_{\text{slab}}$ given in ISO 4037-3:2019 were not taken from the source publication correctly. In conclusion, the CC values given in ISO 4037-3:2019 should be updated in view of the results obtained.

KEYWORDS: Area dosimetry, conversion coefficients, ISO 4037 standard, Monte Carlo, MCNP, personal dosimetry, total air kerma.

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1. Introduction

In ICRP Publication 103 [1] the protection of human health against effects caused by ionizing radiation is based on the prevention of tissue reactions (deterministic effects) and on the limitation of the risks of cancer and hereditary effects (stochastic effects). Two risk-related dosimetric radiation protection quantities are defined. The organ equivalent dose is used to manage and control exposures to ionizing radiation so that deterministic effects are prevented. The effective dose is used to reduce the risks of stochastic effects to the extent reasonably achievable [1]. These quantities are not measurable directly. Therefore, surrogate operational quantities aimed for measurement and instrument calibration are defined in the ICRU Report 39 [2] and later in the ICRU Report 51 [3], providing acceptable and mostly conservative estimates of the protection quantities. Two groups of operational quantities were introduced: for monitoring of personal exposure, and for area monitoring at workplaces and the environment.

The methods for calibrating and determining the response of area and personal dosimeters and dose rate meters for radiological protection in X-ray and γ -ray reference radiation fields in terms of the ICRU 51 operational quantities are defined by the international standards ISO 4037 [4][5][6][7]. Primary photon dosimetry is described in terms of air kerma. Conversion to the operational quantity of interest is realized by multiplying the air kerma with a conversion coefficient (CC) specific to the given radiation quality. This allows the instrument response to be determined in terms of the operational quantity of interest. ISO 4037-3:2019 (subsequently referred to as ISO 4037-3) provides tables with CC values. Newly published CCs in literature (e.g., [8]) were used to extend the range of CCs presented in the previous version [9]. CC values can be directly taken from ISO 4037-3 when matched reference radiation fields are established according to the specific requirements of ISO 4037-1 [4]. Otherwise, the CC value has to be obtained either by the direct measurement of the operational quantity under consideration using a secondary standard compliant with the requirements defined in [5], or by X-ray spectrometry. In the latter case, the CC values for mono-energetic photons taken from [6] should be used to calculate the average CC value for the given radiation quality from the measured spectral distribution of photon fluence [10][11][12].

CC values for mono-energetic photons in [6] were taken from various sources available before its publication, mainly adopted from ICRU 57 [13] but also from others. This inevitably resulted in a data set of differently determined values; some of which were obtained with air kerma factors and a phantom located in vacuum, while others considered electron transport in air [14]. Some were obtained using collision kerma only [15], whereas others were derived using total air kerma, or such information was not mentioned at all. Finally, some references in ICRU 57 are unpublished. Furthermore, for several operational quantities, some tabulated mono-energetic CC values were interpolated from original data and extrapolated at very low photon energies. In addition, this might increase the uncertainty. To obtain a mean CC value for the X-ray fluence spectrum of interest, tabulated mono-energetic CC values from ISO 4037-3 have to be interpolated, which may lead to an inaccurate value if an unsuitable interpolation method is used as was previously investigated in [16]. In line with the recommendation given in ICRU 57 [13], ICRP 116 [17] suggests a four-point (cubic) Lagrangian interpolation formula in a linear-log graph scale. However, for some CC values, namely for low energy photons, a linear-linear interpolation was considered more appropriate [16] but this is also questionable. As suggested in [18] and applied by the same author later [8],[19], an interpolation method should be chosen appropriately and checked to avoid oscillations between the sparsely spaced tabulated data points. This is especially important for narrow X-ray radiation qualities [4], where the whole spectrum may fit in between just two or three consecutive tabulated CC data points.

The aim of this work is to provide a new, consistent determination of mono-energetic values of CCs for all operational quantities considered in ISO 4037-3 and for a much larger number of photon

127 energies. This removes the necessity to test interpolation methods to avoid errors resulting from possible
128 improper interpolation between tabulated mono-energetic CC values.

129 The photon energies from 2 keV to 50 MeV considered in this work encompass the whole energy
130 range for testing and calibration of instruments in X-ray radiation, ^{137}Cs , ^{60}Co and high-energy fields.
131 The impact of the newly calculated mono-energetic CC values on the CC values for the reference
132 radiation qualities defined in [4] will be the scope of another publication.

133 A minor goal of this work is to answer the question of which data in ISO 4037-3 for mono-energetic
134 photons provides CCs from the total air kerma and which from the collision air kerma. This has been
135 discussed in the past, e.g., section 3.4 in [19], “Collisional air kerma or total air kerma” in [18] and
136 “Total air kerma or collisional air kerma” in [8]. The presented work provides the answers.

137 New operational quantities, for which ICRP/ICRU reference phantoms of the human body [20] are
138 used as a basis for calculations, were proposed in the ICRU Report 95 [21]. It was published in 2020
139 and aimed to replace the current operational quantities considered in ISO 4037. The recommended new
140 operational quantities are personal dose and ambient dose, as measures of effective dose used in the
141 limitation and optimization of protection against stochastic effects, and personal absorbed dose and
142 directional absorbed dose as measures of local absorbed dose to the lens of the eye and to local skin to
143 set limits to prevent deterministic effects [21]. However, the implementation of ICRU 95 quantities into
144 practice is complicated, especially for manufacturers of measuring devices because it would usually
145 require mechanical and software modifications of the dosimetry systems [22]. For some combinations
146 of a dosimetry system, new quantity, particle type and energy range modifications are even impossible
147 without an increase of the measurement uncertainty and significant rise in the cost of the detector
148 [23],[24],[25]. The authors of ICRU 95 anticipate that the time required for incorporation of
149 recommendations into safety standards and legislation can last as long as 20 years. Therefore, the current
150 personal and area operational quantities for radiation protection are still relevant and their improvement
151 is of interest.

152 The effort leading to the presented results was driven by discrepancies in ISO 4037-3 data found
153 during the work on a joint European metrological research project entitled “Harmonisation, update and
154 implementation of standards related to radiation protection dosimeters for photon radiation“ [26]
155 (22NRM07 GuideRadPROS). The 3-year project started in 2023 is led by the Finnish radiation and
156 nuclear safety authority (STUK) and aims to provide guidance and protocols to metrology institutes,
157 standardization bodies, and regulators for a consistent and harmonized approach to radiation protection
158 measurements and calibrations following the ISO 4037 standard series [4][5][6][7].

159 2. Materials and methods

160 2.1 Basic terms

161 Absorbed dose in a given volume of matter, D , in unit of Gy is the quotient of the mean energy imparted
162 by ionizing radiation to this volume of matter and its mass [27].

163 Charged-particle equilibrium (CPE) at a point (volume of interest) exists if the distribution of the
164 charged-particle radiance with respect to energy is constant within distances equal to the maximum
165 charged-particle range [22], i.e., throughout a sufficiently small volume. Therefore, the sums of the
166 energies (excluding rest energies) of the charged particles entering and leaving the volume are equal
167 [17].

168 Kerma, K , is the quotient of the mean sum of the initial kinetic energies of all the charged particles
169 liberated in a given volume of matter by the incident uncharged particles, and the mass of matter within
170 this volume [27]. It can be also calculated from equation (1), where Φ is the uncharged-particle fluence,
171 E is the uncharged-particle energy, $\frac{\mu_{\text{en}}}{\rho}$ is the mass energy-absorption coefficient of the material for
172 uncharged particles of energy E , and g is the fraction of the energy of the liberated secondary charged
173 particles that is lost by radiative processes.

$$K = \Phi \cdot E \cdot \frac{\mu_{\text{en}}}{\rho} \frac{1}{(1 - g)} \quad (1)$$

K , also referred to as the total kerma, can be divided into the collision kerma, K_{coll} , and the radiative kerma, K_{rad} , according to equation (2). K_{coll} is realized by ionization and excitation energy losses of charged particles, while the K_{rad} accounts for radiative energy losses of charged particles. K_{coll} is measurable with ionization chambers and approaches absorbed dose to the degree that charged-particle equilibrium exists, that radiative losses are negligible, and that the kinetic energy of the uncharged particles is large compared with the binding energy of the liberated charged particles [27].

$$K = K_{\text{coll}} + K_{\text{rad}}; \quad K_{\text{coll}} = K \cdot (1 - g) \approx D; \quad K_{\text{rad}} = K \cdot g \quad (2)$$

Often, Monte Carlo radiation transport codes take advantage of $K_{\text{coll}} \approx D$ and absorbed dose is determined using the kerma approximation, which usually allows for much faster calculations because time-consuming electron transport is not required. In ISO 4037-3 the CCs are defined for air kerma free-in-air, K_a , with the assumption of negligible radiative kerma up to the energy of ^{60}Co radiation (with an assumed mean energy of 1.25 MeV).

Dose equivalent, H , in unit of Sv is given by the product of D at a point in tissue or organ and the quality factor Q , which equals to 1 Sv/Gy for photons [3]. Selection of a phantom, the depth in the phantom and the radiation field defines the exposure situation and distinguishes between different dose equivalent operational quantities.

ICRU 4-element tissue has a density of $1.0 \text{ g}\cdot\text{cm}^{-3}$ and a mass composition of 76.2 % oxygen, 11.1 % carbon, 10.1 % hydrogen, and 2.6 % nitrogen [2].

The ICRU sphere is defined as a sphere with a diameter of 30 cm and filled with ICRU 4-element tissue. It is anticipated that this phantom adequately approximates scattering and attenuation of radiation fields in the human body [2].

An expanded radiation field is defined as a hypothetical field in which the fluence and its direction and energy distribution have the same values throughout the whole volume of interest as in the actual field at the point of reference [2]. An expanded and aligned radiation field is obtained if all radiation is aligned in the expanded radiation field so that it is opposed to a radius vector Ω specified for the ICRU sphere [2]. See also visualizations in [28].

2.2 Operational quantities

Each quantity represents the dose equivalent in a point at the given depth of a specified phantom irradiated with an expanded or with an expanded and aligned radiation field.

2.2.1 Area dosimetry

The relevant quantities for area dosimetry used for workplace and environmental monitoring are the directional dose equivalent, $H'(d, \Omega)$, and the ambient dose equivalent, $H^*(10)$. The $H'(d, \Omega)$ at a point in a radiation field is the dose equivalent that would be produced by the corresponding expanded field in the ICRU sphere at a depth, d , on a radius in a specified direction Ω . For unidirectional incidence of the radiation beams (during calibrations and calculations of CC values) Ω is replaced by α , the angle between the direction Ω and the radius opposing the direction of the field. $H'(3)$ and $H'(0.07)$ are the estimates for organ equivalent doses to the lens of the eye at a depth of 3 mm and local skin at a depth of 0.07 mm, which set limits to prevent deterministic effects. The $H^*(10)$ at a point in a radiation field is the dose equivalent that would be produced by the corresponding expanded and aligned field in the ICRU sphere at a depth of 10 mm on the radius opposing the direction of the aligned field. $H^*(10)$ is an estimate of effective dose, on which limits are set to minimize stochastic effects [17].

2.2.2 Personal dosimetry

The relevant quantity for personal dosimetry used for individual monitoring is the personal dose equivalent, $H_p(d)$. It is the dose equivalent in soft tissue at a depth of d mm below a specified point on the human body, $H_p(d)$. The specified point is usually given by the position where the individual dosimeter is worn [17]. $H_p(3)$ and $H_p(0.07)$ are the estimates for organ equivalent doses to the lens of the eye and local skin at the respective depths of 3 mm and 0.07 mm. $H_p(10)$ is an estimate of effective dose. For the purpose of instruments calibration and tests, the body is approximated by a phantom suitable for the intended purpose of the instrument. The following phantoms are defined for personal dosimetry: an ICRU slab phantom [29] (width \times height \times depth = 30 cm \times 30 cm \times 15 cm) for $H_p(0.07; \alpha)$ and $H_p(10; \alpha)$ in the whole body, a cylindrical phantom [30] (height \times diameter = 20 cm \times \varnothing 20 cm) for $H_p(3; \alpha)$ in eye lens, a rod phantom [31] (height \times diameter = 30 cm \times \varnothing 1.9 cm) for $H_p(0.07)$ in fingers, and a pillar phantom [32] (height \times diameter = 30 cm \times \varnothing 7.3 cm) for $H_p(0.07)$ in wrists and ankles. All phantoms consist of the ICRU 4-element tissue. However, the ICRU 4-element tissue cannot be fabricated [33], therefore, to mimic their backscatter for dosimeter calibrations, the phantoms are substituted by polymethylmethacrylate (PMMA) phantoms [6] of the same outer dimensions but filled with water, except for the rod, which is solid PMMA. Nevertheless, no correction factors are applied for possible differences in back-scatter properties as they are considered to be negligible [6]. The ICRU 4-element tissue is used in all Monte Carlo simulations performed in this work.

2.3 Conversion coefficients

In ISO 4037-3 [6] the operational quantities, $H(d)$, are determined as a product of the total air kerma, K_a , and the appropriate conversion coefficient, h_K , specific for the operational quantity and the radiation quality under consideration. The CC values are provided therein for mono-energetic photons and for reference radiation fields.

2.4 Secondary charged particle equilibrium

In line with assumptions of ISO 4037-3, all CCs presented in this paper were calculated using the kerma-approximation method and are valid under secondary CPE and hence completed build-up. For tests of instruments according to [5] or [34] and using CC values in [6] or in this paper, CPE is achieved by adding a layer of PMMA of sufficient thickness directly in front of the instrument or dosimeter-phantom set-up [34]. Otherwise, the deviations of the dose from its value under CPE depend on the experimental set-up being used, which precludes the use of universally applicable CC values [6]. A layer of 3 mm has been found to be sufficient to establish CPE for the radiation fields of ^{137}Cs and ^{60}Co [35] while a layer of 25 mm is necessary for the high-energy radiation fields R-C and R-F with 4.4 MeV and (6-7) MeV [36]. The modification of the radiation field induced by the 3 mm PMMA plate is considered negligible for ^{137}Cs and ^{60}Co . On the other hand, the absorption in the 25 mm PMMA plate is not negligible for the R-C and R-F fields and it is treated with a correction $k_{\text{PMMA}} < 1$ in ISO 4037-3 [6]. In the case of filtered X-ray radiation qualities, the use of the PMMA plate is not necessary [6]. The presented work did not consider any build-up plate as CPE was assumed for all photon energies whilst undertaking the calculations by turning off the electron transport, see below.

2.5 Renormalized or unrenormalized Scofield photoeffect cross sections

The unrenormalized Scofield photoeffect data have been adopted for a long time, for example, in the XCOM database [37] and the Electron Photon Interaction Cross Sections (EPICS) [38] used by the MCNP software. On the other hand, the unrenormalized data modified with a normalization screening correction [39], referred to as renormalized photoeffect cross sections, have been more recently adopted

in PENELOPE Monte Carlo software [40] for all elements and were introduced to a more general audience in the ICRU 90 publication [41] for air, water, carbon (graphite) only, but not for the ICRU 4-element tissue. Consideration of renormalized photoeffect cross sections decreases the total cross section in air by about 2.5 %, 1.5 %, 0.5 %, and 0.1 % for photon energies of 20 keV, 54 keV, 85 keV and 160 keV respectively, which may, ultimately, influence the CC values. For detailed discussion about the renormalization of photoeffect cross sections, the reader is referred to chapter 6.1 in the ICRU 90 report [41].

ICRU 90 presented a comparison of measurements and theoretical predictions of the total mass attenuation coefficient in air, $\left(\frac{\mu}{\rho}\right)_{\text{air}}$, indicating that, in most cases, a better agreement was obtained with renormalized photoeffect cross sections. However, the results were not fully convincing, leading the ICRU 90 authors to not finally recommend the use of renormalized cross sections. Eventually, the authors of ICRU 95 did so by providing fluence to air kerma conversion coefficients for renormalized cross sections (table A.6 in [21]). Similarly, the Consultative Committee for Ionizing Radiation (CCRI(I)) accepted a recommendation of an ad hoc committee formed from CCRI(I) representatives with the goal to review the ICRU Report 90 and make recommendations for its implementation. The committee concluded that a general recommendation to adopt renormalized cross-sections seemed appropriate but kept space for metrology institutes to evaluate the impact of their choice of cross-sections, if appropriate [42].

Another discussion on the application of a normalization screening correction was presented in a document dedicated to EPICS cross section data [43]. Therein, it was noted that the experimental data are scarce and often contradictory; therefore it is not clear as to whether or not the renormalization should be applied and it may take a long time to reach a final decision on that question. Thus, the author of [43] concluded that the 2017 update of the EPICS database should keep unrenormalized data. This decision is still valid [44].

Due to the unclear situation, it is suggested to solve this ambiguity by a new investigation at the international level to finally decide which photoeffect cross sections to use whether globally or for specific elements [45]. As mentioned above, further investigations were also recommended in [42].

For these reasons, in this work, the unrenormalized XCOM cross section library was used for both air and ICRU 4-element tissue.

2.6 Potential photon-neutron contribution

As the CC were calculated for photon energies up to 50 MeV, photo-neutrons being produced in the ICRU 4-element tissue phantoms could potentially contribute to the absorbed dose. This could, however, be ruled out as calculations made earlier in human like (tissue) phantoms showed no significant contributions, see section “Simulations” in [46].

2.7 Monte Carlo radiation transport simulations

2.7.1 General setting

Monte Carlo (MC) radiation transport simulations were carried out by means of the general-purpose code MCNPX 2.7.E [47] for the coupled transport of ionizing radiation particles. However, only photons were transported in the simulations using the electron-photon relaxation library EPRDATA14 [48] supplied by the MCNP developers. The library is based on EPICS2014 data, where the cross-section tables for the interaction of photons with matter were taken from the Evaluated Photon Data Library, '97 Version (EPDL97) [49]. The rough estimate of the maximum uncertainty of EPDL97 data is 5 %, 2 %, and (1-2) % for photons with an energy of (1-5) keV, (5-100) keV, and (0.1-10) MeV respectively [49]. The photon energy cutoff was 1 keV. A planar circular or rectangular source, as appropriate for

the given phantom, created an expanded and aligned radiation field of mono-energetic photons by emitting a unidirectional beam towards the phantom. The beam was wide enough to cover the whole cross section of a phantom, even if the phantom was rotated (see Figures 1 and 2). The phantom was surrounded by vacuum. No material was included in between the source and the phantom, except for an air layer 0.1 μm thick for the purpose of K_a calculation validation (section 2.7.7).

Every simulation run generated 3×10^{10} primary particles, except for those with a slab phantom when the run was terminated after dropping the statistical uncertainty, u , below 0.1 %. Many CCs were calculated in one run, which did not allow the same statistical uncertainty for all CC values to be reached. Therefore, u of the calculated results varied depending on the photon energy, angle of radiation incidence, the phantom geometry and the size of the scoring volume; but typically did not exceed 0.1 % for slab phantom and 0.05 % for other phantoms. Larger u resulted in the ICRU sphere at $\alpha = 180^\circ$ ($u \lesssim 0.5$ %, but mostly $u < 0.1$ %), in the cylinder phantom at $\alpha = 90^\circ$ ($u \lesssim 1$ %, but mostly $u < 0.3$ %), and when the CC value was lower than about 0.01 Sv/Gy.

2.7.2 Phantom models

All numerical phantoms were composed of the ICRU 4-element tissue with a density of $1.0 \text{ g}\cdot\text{cm}^{-3}$. Their dimensions matched physical phantom definitions presented in section 2.2.2. Visualizations of the ICRU slab and the cylinder phantoms are presented in Figure 1. Visualization of the ICRU sphere model is shown in Figure 2. The slab phantom rotational axis was vertical, passing through the geometrical center of the front surface. The shapes and sizes of the scoring volumes are given in the following sections.

Figure 1: Schematic visualizations of the Monte Carlo models of the ICRU slab (left) and the cylinder (right) phantoms. 1 – the phantom, 2 – scoring volumes (red), 3 – expanded and aligned radiation field.

Figure 2: Schematic visualization of the Monte Carlo model of the ICRU sphere (left). 1 – the ICRU sphere, 2 – scoring volumes (red), 3 – expanded and aligned radiation field. Scoring volumes only are presented also on the right-hand side figure.

2.7.3 Air kerma scoring

The total air kerma, K_a , per source photon was determined analytically according to equation (1) from the photon fluence, obtained as the reciprocal value of the source area, radiative energy losses in air, g_a , used in [21] taken from [50], and the XCOM unrenormalized values of $\frac{\mu_{en}}{\rho}$ for air and mono-energetic photons from ICRU 90 [41] (Table 6.6a therein). $\frac{\mu_{en}}{\rho}$ and g_a values for photon energies not stated in the tables were interpolated using 4-point Lagrange polynomial in log-log scale.

2.7.4 Absorbed dose scoring

The absorbed dose, D , per source photon in the ICRU 4-element tissue phantoms was realized using the F6-type photon tally that is the photon track-length estimator of energy deposition averaged over a volume. Unrenormalized values of $\frac{\mu}{\rho}$ and $\frac{\mu_{en}}{\rho}$ [51] were used, see Appendix B for details. Radiative energy losses were estimated in the MC runs from the cross section for production of bremsstrahlung photons taken from the el03 electron library [52] even when the electron transport was turned off [53].

Independently of the phantom shape, the thickness of scoring volumes was $1 \mu\text{m}$ at $70 \mu\text{m}$ depth and $10 \mu\text{m}$ at 3mm and 10mm depths. The thicknesses were chosen to be much smaller than the depth and smaller than those used in [54].

In the slab phantom, there were 3 rectangular scoring volumes centered on the slab central axis (parallel with the aligned photon field) at a depth of $70 \mu\text{m}$, 3mm , and 10mm . The length of the rectangle side was 1cm . One simulation for each combination of the photon energy and the angle of phantom rotation was required to get the dose at all three depths.

In the cylindrical phantoms (cylinder, pillar, rod) and the ICRU sphere, there were 13 scoring volumes for each depth representing angles of phantom rotation (or, equivalently, the direction of radiation incidence) from 0° to 180° in steps of 15° . Only one simulation run per photon energy was needed to calculate D at all depths and for all rotation angles because of the axial symmetry of the phantoms. Rotation around the main axis of the cylindrical phantoms was assumed. The number of combinations of angles and depths exceeded those presented in ISO 4037-3. However, D at extra angles and depths was calculated at no additional cost of computational time. In the cylindrical phantoms, the scoring volumes were parts of an annulus around the main cylindrical axis with a height of 4mm and limited by angles $\Delta\alpha \pm 1.14^\circ$ around the nominal rotation angle α (Figure 1). Because of the phantom axial symmetry, D in volumes positioned at opposite angles $+\alpha$ and $-\alpha$ was scored together to double the statistics. In the ICRU sphere, the scoring volumes at all angles except 0° and 180° were annuli

around the radius opposing the direction of the aligned field limited by angles $\Delta\alpha \pm 1.0^\circ$ around the nominal angle α (Figure 2). At the angles 0° and 180° , the scoring volumes were truncated cones with a vertex angle of 3° . The extension $\Delta\alpha$ around the nominal value of the angle α was chosen to be much smaller than the α step and also smaller than used in [54] to assure that the $\Delta\alpha$ does not influence the CC values as resulted from supplementary tests and the discussion in [54].

2.7.5 Energy steps

CC values were calculated for the following photon energies: 1 keV steps between 2 keV to 20 keV, with 2 keV steps up to 60 keV, with 5 keV steps up to 100 keV, with 10 keV steps up to 200 keV, and 51 additional photon energies up to 50 MeV selected so as to include (but not be restricted to) the energies stated in ICRU 95 [21] (Table A.6 therein). For the chosen energy steps, it was verified that the type of interpolation had insignificant influence (usually $\lesssim 0.1\%$) on the CC value.

2.7.6 Calculation of conversion coefficients

From the quantities $K_a(E)$ in air for mono-energetic photons of energy E , and $D(d; E, \alpha)$ in ICRU tissue at the depth d in the given phantom rotated by the angle α , the conversion coefficient $h_K(d; E, \alpha)$ was calculated according to equation (3), where $Q = 1 \text{ Sv/Gy}$.

$$h_K(d; E, \alpha) = \frac{Q \cdot D(d; E, \alpha)}{K_a(E)} \quad (3)$$

2.7.7 Internal checks and external validation

Two “internal” checks and one “external” validation were performed to verify the MC simulations.

The first “internal” check was focused on the calculation of K_a . The total air kerma per fluence, K_a/Φ , of primary mono-energetic photons determined by equation (1) was verified by comparison with K_a/Φ calculated internally by MCNP. Φ and K_a were both obtained using F4-type tallies in a $0.1 \mu\text{m}$ thin air layer located just in front of the photon source. The F4-type tally scores an average Φ in a volume calculated from the photon track length in the volume. K_a was derived during the simulation by applying tally multipliers to convert Φ of primary photons to the total K_a using EPRDATA14 cross section library. See Appendix B for an explanation of such definition.

The second “internal” check focused on the method of calculation of D in the phantom. Testing of several tallies, simulation setups, and two versions of MCNP code against the detailed dose calculation with electron transport turned on, and the justification of the tally selection, are presented in Appendix B.

Finally, the “external” validation was performed by comparing the $h'_K(3; E, \alpha)$ values calculated in this work with those calculated in [54] for collision air kerma using the EGSnrc MC code [55]. For the purpose of the comparison, radiative energy losses in air, g_a , used in the presented work were applied to the data from [54], i.e., they were multiplied with $(1 - g_a)$. That work used the same idea for scoring volumes, however, in both works the Monte Carlo codes, cross-section data, and the thickness and the width of the scoring volumes differed.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1 Internal checks and external validation of MC calculations

K_a/Φ , calculated with MCNP and those obtained using equation (1) were compared. Their RD, expressed as the RD of CC values, is shown in section 3.5. The RD within $\pm 0.3\%$ in the whole energy range demonstrates that the radiation field geometry was correctly set up and the MCNP cross sections

were correctly used. It is assumed that the obtained RD are dominated by the difference in g_a values, interpolation between tabulated cross section data and MCNP code treatment of available cross section data when calculating the selected tally.

Results of testing of dose in tissue calculations are summarized in Appendix B. The selected tally for dose calculations was the F6:P tally derived using photon-only transport. It was presented that the systematic uncertainty given by the difference between the dose obtained with the *F8-type tally and the F6:P-type tally with electron transport turned off did not exceed 1.2 %.

Comparison of the RD of $h'_K(3; E, \alpha)$ values calculated in this work and those presented in [54] (Table A2 therein), corrected by $(1-g_a)$ values used in this work, is shown in Figure 3. The RD typically varied between -1% and $+0.5\%$. Such RD can be attributed to statistical uncertainties of MC simulations (“much smaller than 1%” in [54] and $u < 0.15\%$ (or $u < 0.5\%$ for $\alpha = 180^\circ$) in this work if $h'_K(3; E, \alpha) > 0.01$ Sv/Gy), cross-section tables, interpolation of cross-section values, and differences in Monte Carlo codes. An RD of (1-2) % was observed at the energy of 120 keV at all angles. The reason was the difference of about 1.4 % between the interpolation result for this specific energy if calculated using a 4-point log-log interpolation as in this work or with a 2-point log-log interpolation used in [54] (Table A1 therein) and also in ICRU 95 [21] (Table A.6 therein). The 2-point log-log interpolation result was applied to derive K_a/Φ and, accordingly, the corresponding CC values in [54]. A slight deviation of the values from a smooth line in the plots in Figure 3 (right) indicates that the 4-point log-log interpolation provides more consistent results for an energy of 120 keV.

Figure 3: Left - Relative difference (RD) between $h'_K(3; E, \alpha)$ calculated in this work (h_{MCNP}) and in [54] (h_{EGS}) for various rotation angles α for mono-energetic photons; $RD = h_{MCNP}/h_{EGS} - 1$. Right - Systematic deviation between h_{MCNP} (dots) and h_{EGS} (crosses) for 120 keV photons, presented for selected α only.

The very good agreement with literature data [54] validates the MC model and the methodology used in this paper.

Finally, as published in [54], the influence of the size of scoring volumes was discussed and it was concluded that no systematic deviations from the calculations with the original scoring volumes (a thickness of 20 μm and a maximum width of about 10 mm) were observed at the reference depth of 3 mm. Because the scoring volumes used in the presented work were smaller, the conclusions made in [54] are valid for this work as well.

3.2 Conversion coefficients for area dosimetry

3.2.1 Conversion coefficient $h'_K(0.07; E, \alpha)$

The calculated values of $h'_K(0.07; E, \alpha)$ from K_a to $H'(0.07)$ for mono-energetic and parallel photon radiation and angles of incidence α stated in ISO 4037-3 [6] are presented in Figure C1 and Table D1

in the Appendix C and Appendix D, respectively. The mentioned figure also shows the data used in ISO 4037-3, which were taken in the limited range up to 1.25 MeV from ICRU 57 [13], which adopted original results from [57]. The source of interpolated CC values used in [6] is not clear. Referenced works are [16] and [56]. However, the reference [56] does not include $h'_K(0.07; E, \alpha)$ for mono-energetic photons. In addition, ISO 4037-3 states some of the interpolated CC values given in [16], while another interpolated CC values and all extrapolated CC values presented there are different.

The RD between CC values in ISO 4037-3 and in the presented work varied within $\pm 3\%$ for $E \geq 10$ keV and $\alpha \leq 60^\circ$. For $E < 10$ keV or $\alpha > 60^\circ$, the RD was much larger. Obviously, below 10 keV the discrepancy was caused by the 2-point linear-linear interpolation applied on ICRU 57 data in [16]. At $\alpha \geq 75^\circ$ the discrepancy might be caused by larger statistical uncertainties of ICRU 57 data as suggested in [54] and by averaging of the calculated absorbed dose over the dose gradients in larger scoring volumes being used in calculations in [57] and adopted by ICRU 57. The latter is especially the case for $\alpha = 90^\circ$ as already noted by other authors [54],[58].

$h'_K(0.07; E, \alpha)$ values cited in ICRU 57 were derived for collision air kerma [57]. This was confirmed by comparison of the CC values for $E = 10$ MeV and $\alpha = 0^\circ$, which are 1.10 Sv/Gy in ICRU 57 (Table A.23 therein) and 1.065 Sv/Gy in this work. Their RD of 3.2 % is much larger than the RD for other energies. This is explained by a g_a value equal to 0.0373 ($(1-g_a)^{-1} = 1.039$) used in the presented work for the photon energy of 10 MeV, whereas ICRU 57 data were adopted by ISO 4037-3 without a correction for radiative energy losses as only results up to 1.25 MeV were used for $h'_K(0.07; E, \alpha)$.

3.2.2 Conversion coefficient $h'_K(3; E, \alpha)$

The calculated values of $h'_K(3; E, \alpha)$ from K_a to $H'(3)$ for mono-energetic and parallel photon radiation and angles of incidence α stated in ISO 4037-3 [6] are presented in Figure C2 and Table D2 in Appendix C and Appendix D, respectively. The mentioned figure also shows the ISO 4037-3 data, which used results from [54] derived using collision air kerma. In the limited range up to 10 MeV adopted in [6], the original results were recalculated into total air kerma by applying g_a values from [5] determined according to [59]. Within this energy range, the tabulated g_a values [5] matched the g_a values used in the presented paper. The original data were used for the validation of the MC model in the presented work and the RD were already analyzed in section 3.1. Therefore, any difference deviating from the results presented in Figure 3 could be caused by the rounding to only three significant digits in [6].

3.2.3 Conversion coefficient $h^*_K(10; E)$

The calculated values of $h^*_K(10; E)$ from K_a to $H^*(10)$ for mono-energetic and parallel photon radiation are presented in Figure C3 and Table D3 in Appendix C and Appendix D, respectively. The mentioned figure also shows the data used in ISO 4037-3 [6] taken from [13] and [16]. The RD of the CC values from ISO 4037-3 to those of the presented work varied within $\pm 3\%$ for $E \geq 15$ keV. Below 15 keV, where $h^*_K(10; E) < 0.2$ Sv/Gy, the differences were larger.

The ISO 4037-3 data were taken from ICRU 57 [13], which were obtained from ICRU 47 [29] applying updated $\frac{\mu_{en}}{\rho}$ data. CC values in ICRU 47 were compiled from several Monte Carlo simulations and experiments published between 1979 and 1985. These datasets were evaluated in [60] and [14]. To obtain mean $h^*_K(10; E)$ values, the first work calculated an average weighed by statistical and systematic uncertainties subsequently fitted with spline functions. The latter work proposed an empirical analytic function of energy valid above 20 keV. For $E \leq 20$ keV, an average of three results available in literature at that time was used. ICRU 47 stated that mean $h^*_K(10; E)$ resulted from both evaluations differ by $\pm 2\%$ up to 3 MeV, which was less than the uncertainties in the calculations. Therefore, the analytic function was adopted for calculation of $h^*_K(10; E)$ values tabulated in ICRU 47 and later adopted by

ICRU 57. For full discussion and references to original papers see [13] and [29]. The analytic function was derived in [14] and it was also presented in [29] and [28].

Although the ICRU 47 gives the equation for the total air kerma (section A.2.1 in [29]), the provided $h^*_{\kappa}(10; E)$ values derived from the analytic function, and subsequently adopted by ICRU 57, were determined for collision air kerma. It can be traced to original works, e.g., [61], and it is also obvious by comparing the $h^*_{\kappa}(10; E)$ value for $E = 10$ MeV of 1.10 Sv/Gy and 1.05 Sv/Gy given in ICRU 57 and in the presented work, respectively. The resulting RD of 4.5 % is largely outside the range of RD at energies $\lesssim 1.5$ MeV and it corresponds rather to the radiative energy loss of $g_a = 0.0373$ ($((1-g_a)^{-1} = 1.039)$) for 10 MeV photons. Also, ISO 4037-3 states that g_a values from [5] were applied to the $h^*_{\kappa}(10; E)$ values when they were adopted from ICRU 57.

In conclusion, the RD between the presented and ISO 4037-3 $h^*_{\kappa}(10; E)$ values are in line with the RD of ~ 2 % between previous evaluations, which ICRU 57 considered as a good agreement [13]. The specific consequence is the deviation of the presented and ISO 4037-3 $h^*_{\kappa}(10; E)$ values for ^{137}Cs and ^{60}Co radionuclides commonly used for dosimeter calibrations. The RD observed is -2.8 %. The presented $h^*_{\kappa}(10; E)$ is 1.176 Sv/Gy for mono-energetic 662 keV photons of ^{137}Cs and 1.128 Sv/Gy for 1.25 MeV photons of ^{60}Co (approximate average of dominant 1.17 MeV and 1.33 MeV photons emitted by ^{60}Co), while the ISO 4037-3 gives 1.21 Sv/Gy and 1.16 Sv/Gy for ^{137}Cs and ^{60}Co , respectively [6]. It is anticipated that these differences will also propagate average $h^*_{\kappa}(10; E)$ values calculated for a realistic energy fluence spectrum of ^{137}Cs and ^{60}Co .

3.3 Conversion coefficients for personal dosimetry

3.3.1 Conversion coefficient $h_{p\kappa}(0.07; E)_{\text{rod}}$

The calculated values of $h_{p\kappa}(0.07; E)_{\text{rod}}$ from K_a to $H_p(0.07)$ for mono-energetic and parallel photon radiation and the rod phantom are presented in Figure C4 and Table D4 in Appendix C and Appendix D, respectively. The mentioned figure also shows the data used in ISO 4037-3 taken from [62] and [16]. Except for 3 keV, the RD to the presented work varied within -0.5 % and $+1.5$ %, which can be attributed to statistical uncertainties of MC simulations ($u = (0.1-1.0)$ % in [62], Table 1 therein), the rounding to only three significant digits in [6], interpolation used by [16], and neglect of radiative energy losses. The RD reaching 3.5 % was found for the lowest photon energy of 3 keV. CC value for this energy used in [6] was an extrapolated value from [16]. $h_{p\kappa}(0.07; E)_{\text{rod}}$ values were given for collision air kerma in [62] and were adopted by [6] without any change, as the maximum E is 1.25 MeV.

3.3.2 Conversion coefficient $h_{p\kappa}(0.07; E)_{\text{pill}}$

The calculated values of $h_{p\kappa}(0.07; E)_{\text{pill}}$ from K_a to $H_p(0.07)$ for mono-energetic and parallel photon radiation and the pillar phantom are presented in Figure C5 and Table D5 in Appendix C and Appendix D, respectively. The mentioned figure also shows the data used in ISO 4037-3 taken from [62]. Very good agreement was observed with the RD to the presented work varying between -0.6 % and $+1.1$ %. These limited differences can be attributed to the statistical uncertainties of MC simulations ($u = (0.1-0.7)$ % in [62], Table 1 therein), the rounding to only three significant digits in [6], and neglect of radiative energy losses. $h_{p\kappa}(0.07; E)_{\text{pill}}$ values were given for collision air kerma in [62] and were adopted by [6] without any change, as the maximum E is 1.25 MeV.

3.3.3 Conversion coefficient $h_{p\kappa}(0.07; E, \alpha)_{\text{slab}}$

The calculated values of $h_{p\kappa}(0.07; E, \alpha)_{\text{slab}}$ from K_a to $H_p(0.07)$ for mono-energetic and parallel photon radiation, the slab phantom, and angles of incidence α stated in ISO 4037-3 are presented in Figure C6 and Table D6 in Appendix C and Appendix D, respectively. The mentioned figure also shows the data

used in [6] taken from [63] for $E < 10$ keV and from [64] for other photon energies. For $E < 10$ keV the RD was typically within ± 1 % except for $E = 3$ keV, where the photons are, due to their low energy, already significantly affected by scattering and absorption before reaching the scoring volume; therefore, even small differences in radiation transport parameters used by different authors such as the cross sections may result in markedly different CCs. For higher energies, the RD varied within ± 2.5 % at $\alpha \leq 15^\circ$, while for larger angles the RD varied from -5 % to $+10$ % (except for 10 keV and 75° with RD of -12 %).

A closer comparison of $h_{pK}(0.07; E, \alpha)_{\text{slab}}$ for $E \geq 10$ keV revealed an error in the ISO 4037-3 [6] data. Values $h_{pK}(0.07; E, \alpha)_{\text{slab}}$ presented in [64] are denoted with an incorrect depth d and the incorrect angle of radiation incidence α in ISO 4037-3. Correctly, the $h_{pK}(0.07; E, \alpha)_{\text{slab}}$ provided in ISO 4037-3 are valid for the depth $d = 0$ mm and $\alpha = 15^\circ, 30^\circ, 45^\circ, 60^\circ, 75^\circ$, and 82.5° according to data given in [64], instead of $d = 0.07$ mm and $\alpha = 0^\circ, 15^\circ, 30^\circ, 45^\circ, 60^\circ$, and 75° , respectively, as stated in ISO 4037-3, Table 33 therein [6]). Also, this is the reason for apparent outliers at $E = 10$ keV at all angles, because the depth and angle have the largest influence on the CC value at lowest E . When the results for $h_{pK}(0.07; E, \alpha)_{\text{slab}}$ from this work and those published in [64] are compared for the correct d and α , the following RD valid for all α are obtained: -0.4 % to $+0.7$ % for $E \geq 50$ keV (except for $E = 70$ keV with RD systematically around $+1.6$ % assumed to be caused by the interpolation method) and 0.2 % to 1.6 % for $E < 50$ keV. These RD are comparable to RD obtained for another CCs in this work. $h_{pK}(0.07; E, \alpha)_{\text{slab}}$ values were given for collision air kerma in [64], but they are stated for total air kerma in [6] obtained by applying g_a values from [5] to the original data, i.e., by multiplication with $(1-g_a)$.

Another set of $h_{pK}(0.07; E, \alpha)_{\text{slab}}$ values in the E range from 5 keV to 1 MeV was provided in [13], which was taken from an unpublished study [65]. Comparing to the data from this work, the RD stayed within ± 0.5 % for $E \geq 50$ keV and for all α . For lower photon energies the RD varied between -0.6 % and $+1.9$ % for all α . This comparison confirmed that the $h_{pK}(0.07; E, \alpha)_{\text{slab}}$ values for mono-energetic photons provided in ISO 4037-3 [6] were adopted incorrectly from the original publication and should be updated.

3.3.4 Conversion coefficient $h_{pK}(3; E, \alpha)_{\text{cyl}}$

The calculated values of $h_{pK}(3; E, \alpha)_{\text{cyl}}$ from K_a to $H_p(3)$ for mono-energetic and parallel photon radiation, the cylinder phantom, and angles of incidence α stated in ISO 4037-3 are presented in Figure C7 and Table D7 in Appendix C and Appendix D, respectively. The mentioned figure also shows the data used in [6] taken from [8] for $E < 10$ keV and from [66] for other photon energies. Very good agreement was achieved within ± 1 % for $10 \text{ keV} < E \lesssim 2 \text{ MeV}$. Slightly larger RD were obtained for lower photon energies, however, for all such energies the CC value was < 0.06 Sv/Gy, therefore the discrepancies might be dominated by statistical uncertainties. Larger RD up to 1.5 % were observed for $E \gtrsim 2 \text{ MeV}$.

According to a statement in section 2.3.2 in [66], total air kerma was considered. This was confirmed by a comparison with results obtained by a similar group of authors in their previous publication [67], where total air kerma was used. For example, $h_{pK}(3; E, \alpha)_{\text{cyl}}$ value for $E = 10 \text{ MeV}$ and $\alpha = 0^\circ$ reported by both works differed by 0.2 % only verifying that the same approach was used. ISO 4037-3 [6] adopted the data without a correction to radiative energy losses. The cause of the discrepancy for $E \gtrsim 2 \text{ MeV}$ was not found, but it may be speculated that there is a possible difference between radiative energy losses in photon cross section tables MPLIB04 [68] used in [66] and EPRDATA library and g_a values used in the presented work.

3.3.5 Conversion coefficient $h_{pK}(10; E, \alpha)_{\text{slab}}$

The calculated values of $h_{pK}(10; E, \alpha)_{\text{slab}}$ from K_a to $H_p(10)$ for mono-energetic and parallel photon radiation, the slab phantom, and angles of incidence α stated in ISO 4037-3 are presented in Figure C8

1
2
3 573 and Table D8 in Appendix C and Appendix D, respectively. The mentioned figure also shows the data
4 574 used in [6] taken from ICRU 57 [13] and interpolated in [16]. ICRU 57 data consist of results compiled
5 575 from [64] and from unpublished work [65], which revised calculations presented in [69] originally
6 576 adopted in ICRU 47 [29], all derived using collision kerma. The compilation method used in ICRU 57
7 577 is unknown. However, the RD between ICRU 57 and [64] is within $\pm 0.7\%$ for $E \geq 20$ keV and $\alpha \leq 60^\circ$,
8 578 and slightly higher otherwise. When adopted by ISO 4037-3, the CC values were corrected for radiative
9 579 energy losses by applying g_a values from [5].

10 580 If ISO 4037-3 is compared to the presented work, the RD is typically within $\pm 1.5\%$ for $E > 30$ keV
11 581 (or $E > 50$ keV for $\alpha = 75^\circ$), except for a few scattered values occurring mainly for photons with
12 582 $E \geq 3$ MeV. For low E , the RD were much larger and reached -12% . The cause of these larger RD is
13 583 unknown but may be contributed by a) the difference in $\frac{\mu_{en}}{\rho}$ for elements in ICRU 4-element tissue in
14 584 [64] ($\frac{\mu_{en}}{\rho}$ taken from [70]) and in this work (e.g. RD of $\sim 2\%$ at $E = 10$ keV), b) reported statistical
15 585 uncertainty of CC values up to 8 % for $E \leq 20$ keV in [64], c) steep gradient of CC values for $E \leq 20$ keV
16 586 (see Figure C8) resulting in high sensitivity to radiation transport modeling and scoring of the dose
17 587 quantity, d) for $E < 10$ keV CC values were extrapolated as described in detail in [16] because ICRU 57
18 588 provided the CC values only for $E \geq 10$ keV, and e) CC values for $E \leq 12.5$ keV stated in [13] are small
19 589 and given to one or two significant digits only, which might bias the interpolated and extrapolated CC
20 590 values. As a result, the observed RD may already be relevant for dosimeter calibrations as, for example,
21 591 the value presented in this study for $E = 14$ keV and $\alpha = 0^\circ$, $h_{pK}(10; 14 \text{ keV}, 0^\circ)_{\text{slab}} = 0.183$ Sv/Gy is
22 592 lower by 7.5 % compared to the ISO 4037-3 one.

23 593 3.4 Summary

24 594 Source publications for mono-energetic CCs provided in ISO 4037-3 and the summary of the
25 595 comparison between the presented work and that of [6] are given in Table 1. Moreover, the statistical
26 596 uncertainty and the uncertainty given by the selected method of calculation of the absorbed dose in this
27 597 work are discussed in section 2.7.1 and in Appendix B, respectively. The CC values that resulted from
28 598 this work are available in electronic form [71]. Description of the files is provided in Appendix A.

599 Table 1: Summary of ISO 4037-3:2019 [6] references for conversion coefficients (CC) from air kerma to dose equivalent
 600 quantities for mono-energetic photons and the summary of relative differences (RD) of CC values between this work and
 601 ISO 4037-3.

Conversion coefficient	Main reference ⁽¹⁾	Interpolated values ⁽²⁾	Extrapolated values ⁽²⁾	RD, this work ⁽³⁾
$h'_{\kappa}(0.07; E, \alpha)$	[13] (1998) ⁽⁴⁾	[16] (2000) ⁽⁶⁾ [56] (2007) ⁽⁶⁾	unclear ⁽⁶⁾	$\pm 3\%$ ($E \geq 10$ keV, $\alpha \leq 60^\circ$); much larger RD for $E < 10$ keV or $\alpha > 60^\circ$
$h'_{\kappa}(3; E, \alpha)$	[54] (2017)	none	none	-1% to $+0.5\%$
$h^*_{\kappa}(10; E)$	[13] (1998) ⁽⁴⁾	[16] (2000)	[16] (2000); $E < 10$ keV)	$\pm 3\%$ ($E > 15$ keV); larger for $E \leq 15$ keV)
$h_{\text{pk}}(0.07; E)_{\text{rod}}$	[62] (1995)	[16] (2000)	[16] (2000); $E = 3$ keV)	-0.5% to $+1.5\%$
$h_{\text{pk}}(0.07; E)_{\text{pill}}$	[62] (1995)	none	none	-0.6% to $+1.1\%$
$h_{\text{pk}}(0.07; E, \alpha)_{\text{slab}}$	[64] (1995; $E \geq 10$ keV) ⁽⁵⁾ [63] (1991; $E < 10$ keV)	none	none	$\pm 1\%$ (3 keV $< E < 10$ keV) $\pm 2.5\%$ ($E \geq 10$ keV and $\alpha \leq 15^\circ$) ⁽⁵⁾ ; -5% to $+10\%$ (other E and α) ⁽⁵⁾
$h_{\text{pk}}(3; E, \alpha)_{\text{cyl}}$	[66] (2012)	none	[8] (2012; $E < 10$ keV)	$\pm 1\%$ (10 keV $< E \lesssim 2$ MeV); -1.5% to 0% ($E \gtrsim 2$ MeV); larger for $E \leq 10$ keV
$h_{\text{pk}}(10; E, \alpha)_{\text{slab}}$	[13] (1998) ⁽⁴⁾	[16] (2000)	[16] (2000)	$\pm 1.5\%$ ($E > 30$ keV and $\alpha \leq 60^\circ$, or $E > 50$ keV and $\alpha = 75^\circ$); up to -12% for lower E

602 ⁽¹⁾ Main reference stated in [6];

603 ⁽²⁾ Reference stated in [6] for interpolated/extrapolated data of main reference.

604 ⁽³⁾ Relative difference between this work and [6], outliers not considered; for details see plots in Appendix C.

605 ⁽⁴⁾ ICRU 57 data were taken from various previously published literature.

606 ⁽⁵⁾ Incorrect data were adopted in [6] from the source publication [64].

607 ⁽⁶⁾ References stated in [6]. However, reference [56] does not include $h'_{\kappa}(0.07; E, \alpha)$ for mono-energetic
 608 photons. ISO 4037-3 uses some of the interpolated values given in [16], but another interpolated values and
 609 all extrapolated values differ from those provided in [16].

610 3.5 Correction for the use of another photoeffect cross sections

611 Some Monte Carlo users may calculate K_a using a different $\frac{\mu_{\text{en}}}{\rho}$ dataset for air, e.g. using PENELOPE
 612 or the renormalized XCOM libraries. To get the same numerical value of the appropriate dose equivalent
 613 quantity according to equation (3) as with the $\frac{\mu_{\text{en}}}{\rho}$ dataset for air and CC values used in the presented
 614 work, an energy-dependent correction needs to be applied (equation (4)), assuming that radiative energy
 615 losses in air, $g_a(E)$, are the same.

$$616 \quad K_a(E) = K_{a,\gamma}(E) \cdot \frac{\left(\frac{\mu_{\text{en}}(E)}{\rho}\right)_{\text{XCOM}}}{\left(\frac{\mu_{\text{en}}(E)}{\rho}\right)_{\text{Y}}} \quad (4)$$

617 For PENELOPE and renormalized XCOM datasets from ICRU 90, the numerical values of the
 618 correction are provided in the supplementary file described in Appendix A and visualized in Figure 4.
 619 In equation (4), for photon energy E , the $K_a(E)$ is the total air kerma calculated in this paper derived
 620 with the XCOM unrenormalized $\left(\frac{\mu_{\text{en}}(E)}{\rho}\right)_{\text{XCOM}}$ dataset for air and $K_{a,\gamma}(E)$ is the total air kerma
 621 calculated with a different $\left(\frac{\mu_{\text{en}}(E)}{\rho}\right)_{\text{Y}}$ dataset for air. It is worth to note that, what concerns K_a
 622 measurements with a primary method, the K_a value derived from free-air chamber measurements does
 623 not depend on $\frac{\mu_{\text{en}}}{\rho}$ [72], with the exception of correction factors derived with MC simulations; however,
 624

625 it is stated that the impact on the K_a value is not significant except for the correction for air attenuation
 626 [42]. In contrast, for air-kerma cavity standards, a correction similar to equation (4) would need to be
 627 applied because $\frac{\mu_{en}}{\rho}$ occurs in the corresponding formula for K_a [73]. However, as the ratio
 628 $\left(\frac{\mu_{en}}{\rho}\right)_{\text{air}} / \left(\frac{\mu_{en}}{\rho}\right)_{\text{graphite}}$ is used, the difference introduced by the normalization screening correction
 629 partially cancels out as for both data sets, $\left(\frac{\mu_{en}}{\rho}\right)_{\text{air}}$ and $\left(\frac{\mu_{en}}{\rho}\right)_{\text{graphite}}$, renormalized values are available
 630 in ICRU 90. Therefore, the relative difference (RD) of these ratios determined with unrenormalized and
 631 renormalized datasets does not exceed 1.1 %, with the maximum RD reached at $E = 15$ keV.

633
 634 Figure 4: Relative difference between K_a used in this paper to calculate conversion coefficient values and $K_{a,Y}$ if determined
 635 using XCOM renormalized $\frac{\mu_{en}(E)}{\rho}$ values for air from ICRU 90 (blue circles), PENELOPE $\frac{\mu_{en}(E)}{\rho}$ values for air from ICRU 90
 636 (green triangles), and internally by MCNP with EPRDATA14 cross section tables (red diamonds).

637 4. Conclusions

638 New calculations of conversion coefficients from the total air kerma to all operational dosimetric
 639 quantities used for individual and area monitoring included in ISO 4037-3:2019 standard were
 640 performed by means of Monte Carlo simulations in the MCNP code for mono-energetic photons from
 641 2 keV to 50 MeV using kerma approximation, assuming secondary charged particle equilibrium. As a
 642 finer energy resolution (1 keV steps up to 20 keV, 2 keV steps up to 60 keV, 5 keV steps up to 100 keV,
 643 10 keV steps up to 200 keV, and larger steps above 200 keV) and a wider energy range (from 2 keV up
 644 to 50 MeV) was used in this work, the results allow more accurate determination of mean conversion
 645 coefficients for radiation qualities. This is especially the case for conversion coefficients for which the
 646 tabulated values were obtained by extrapolation or interpolation from the ICRU 57 data (which only
 647 provided data from 5 keV to 1 MeV, e.g., for $h_{pK}(0.07; E, \alpha)_{\text{slab}}$, or 10 keV to 10 MeV for
 648 $h_{pK}(10; E, \alpha)_{\text{slab}}$, having higher or unspecified statistical uncertainties in original works, or when the
 649 tabulated values are scarce, therefore the type of interpolation significantly influences the resulted CC
 650 value. An example of the latter are extreme differences for $h'_{K}(0.07; E, \alpha)$ below 10 keV and for $\alpha \geq 75^\circ$
 651 as those values are zero in ICRU 57.

652 It was confirmed that the ISO 4037-3:2019 values of mono-energetic conversion coefficients are
 653 given for the total air kerma. The exceptions are $h'_{K}(0.07; E, \alpha)$, $h_{pK}(0.07; E)_{\text{rod}}$, and $h_{pK}(0.07; E)_{\text{pill}}$.
 654 However, this seems to be intended as these CCs were provided in the energy range up to 1.25 MeV
 655 only, where the radiative energy losses are assumed negligible.

656 The values of $h_{pK}(0.07; E, \alpha)_{\text{slab}}$ presented in ISO 4037-3:2019 were incorrectly adopted from the
657 original publication and should be updated.. In addition, some observed relative differences between the
658 presented and tabulated conversion coefficients reached values relevant for dosimeter calibrations such
659 as, for example, $h_{pK}(10; E, \alpha)_{\text{slab}}$ at low photon energies. Another example is the relative difference
660 between the presented and the interpolated ISO 4037 $h^*_{K}(10; E)$ values for main energies of photons of
661 ^{137}Cs and ^{60}Co , which reached -2.8% ($h^*_{K}(10; E)$ in this work is lower).

662 The presented new calculations contribute to the improvement of the accuracy in radiation
663 protection dosimetry and the results might be considered in the upcoming update of the ISO 4037
664 standard. The impact of the newly calculated conversion coefficients for mono-energetic photons on the
665 average conversion coefficients for ISO 4037-1:2019 reference radiation qualities will be detailed in a
666 future publication.

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876 **Appendix A: Electronic version of conversion coefficients**

877 Conversion coefficients calculated and presented in this paper are available in electronic form. Two files
878 are provided:

879

- 880 • File 1: A simple file with sheets containing tables with CC values from Appendix D and the
881 numerical values for datasets presented in Figure 4 is available online [71];
- 882 • File 2: A file with comprehensive tables, where it is possible to select a quantity, phantom, depth
883 and an angle of radiation incidence, and the CC values are shown in a table together with
884 tabulated CC values from [6] and their relative differences. Selection of combinations of a
885 quantity, phantom, depth and angle of radiation incidence beyond those stated in ISO 4037-3 is
886 possible. This file is available from the main author upon request. Additional data are presented
887 there:

- 888 ○ CC values calculated for smaller scoring volumes are provided for quantities defined in
889 the ICRU sphere.
- 890 ○ CC values calculated for the rotation of a phantom around the axis transversal to both
891 the direction of radiation incidence and the phantom cylindrical axis are provided for
892 rod, pillar, and cylinder phantoms; this axis passed through the intersection of the
893 phantom surface and the radius opposing the direction of the radiation field.
- 894 ○ CC values calculated for smaller irradiation fields (circular field with a diameter of
895 10 cm and 20 cm) are provided for rod, pillar, and cylinder phantoms for $\alpha = 0^\circ$ of the
896 incidence of the radiation field and for the slab phantom for all α considered in [6].
- 897 ○ Numerical values for datasets presented in Figure 4.

898

899 Both Excel files also contain a short description of MC simulations and visualizations of the MC
900 models.

901 Appendix B: Selection of tally to calculate absorbed dose

902 There are several ways to calculate an estimate of the absorbed dose in MCNP radiation transport code.
 903 The selection of a suitable tally depends on the aim of the MC simulation, types of particles used and
 904 generated, particle energies, availability of cross section data, etc. [53]. To increase the calculation
 905 speed, the CCs in this work were obtained for kerma approximation in the conditions of CPE. Therefore,
 906 electrons were not transported, only photon transport was considered. To ensure that the dose in ICRU
 907 tissue calculated with photon-only transport is reliable, different tally definitions were tested by
 908 comparison with anticipated reference values of the absorbed dose, which is derived by “the dose tally”,
 909 the *F8-tally type, when the electron transport was turned on and in the condition of CPE. Tested tallies
 910 are presented in Table B1. A simple geometry was used. A cylinder was filled with ICRU 4-element
 911 tissue. A thin, scoring volume was located inside the cylinder in a depth corresponding to 1.5 times the
 912 continuous slowing down approximation (CDSA) range for electrons with an energy equal to the energy
 913 of primary photons. CDSA range is the average path length travelled by an electron as it slows down to
 914 rest and its value was taken from ESTAR database [74]. Such depth was sufficient to achieve CPE.
 915

916 Table B1: List of tallies considered for calculation of absorbed dose in tissue.

No.	Tally	Electron transport	Tally description	Reasoning
1	*F8:P,E	On	The difference between the sum of energies entering and leaving the scoring volume. Electron transport used nearest group boundary (“Integrated Tiger Series-style”) energy-indexing algorithm [53] (card DBCN 17j 1).	Expected true value. This is assumed to be the most accurate way to calculate the absorbed dose in MCNPX.
2	*F8:P,E	On	Same as No.1; electron transport used bin-centered (“MCNP-style”) energy-indexing algorithm [53]. Default for MCNPX.	To check the difference between electron transport algorithms.
3	*F8:P,E	On	Same as No.1; calculated with MCNP 6.3 [53]. Electron transport used detailed energy- and step-specific Landau straggling sampling logic, which is default for MCNP 6.3 [53].	To check the difference between electron transport algorithms and MCNP codes.
4	F6:P	On	Photon track-length estimator of average D in a scoring volume using kerma factors from photon cross sections.	Expected to be the same value as No.1.
5	F6:P	Off	Same as No.4.	Tally selected for CC calculations presented in this work.
6	F6:P	Off	Same as No.4; calculated with MCNP 6.3 [53] with the same cross section libraries.	To check the difference between MCNP codes.
7	+F6	Off	Total energy deposition from all particles [53].	Alternative for No.5.
8	F4:P +FM	Off	Photon fluence converted to kerma using a tally multiplier card (fluence multiplied with the atom density, air mass in the scoring volume, the photon total cross section, and the photon kerma factor [51]), definition: FM4 -1 m -5 -6; m = material number.	Alternative for No.5.
9	F4:P +DE/DF	Off	Photon fluence multiplied by energy dependent function defined as $E \cdot \left(\frac{\mu_{en}(E)}{\rho}\right)_{XCOM}$ unrenormalized (taken from [41]) to get collision kerma and hence D .	Collision kerma calculated from fluence using $\frac{\mu_{en}}{\rho}$ from [75].

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Results obtained for energies 0.15 MeV, 0.662 MeV, 1.25 MeV, 10 MeV, 20 MeV, and 30 MeV are presented in Table B2. Absolute values are not important; therefore the results are presented as a relative difference to the results obtained with the *F8:P,E tally (number 1 in Table B1).

Table B2: Relative difference (RD) between the absorbed dose obtained with the *F8-type tally calculated by MCNPX 2.7.E and other tallies, F_x , presented as $F_x/(*F8) - 1$, for several photon energies. Statistical uncertainty is $< 0.01\%$ for F4 and F6 tallies and 0.03% for *F8 tallies, respectively.

Compared tally	RD to *F8-type tally calculated by MCNPX 2.7.E					
	150 keV	662 keV	1.25 MeV	10 MeV	20 MeV	30 MeV
*F8:P,E (No.2 in Table B1)	0.04 %	-0.36 %	-0.90 %	-1.30 %	-1.82 %	-1.70 %
*F8:P,E (MCNP 6.3, No.3 in Table B1)	0.01 %	0.26 %	0.34 %	-0.05 %	0.09 %	0.02 %
F6:P (with electron transport)	0.05 %	-0.17 %	-0.49 %	-0.89 %	-1.09 %	-1.50 %
F6:P	0.05 %	-0.16 %	-0.49 %	-0.82 %	-1.05 %	-1.53 %
F6:P (MCNP 6.3)	0.05 %	-0.17 %	-0.49 %	-0.82 %	-1.03 %	-1.49 %
+F6	0.05 %	-0.16 %	-0.49 %	-0.82 %	-1.05 %	-1.53 %
F4:P +FM	0.05 %	-0.14 %	-0.45 %	-0.12 %	0.98 %	2.22 %
F4:P +DE/DF	0.15 %	-0.55 %	-0.70 %	-3.35 %	-5.97 %	N/A ⁽¹⁾

(1) $\frac{\mu_{en}(E)}{\rho}$ not available for $E = 30$ MeV in XCOM database [75].

The findings valid for the calculations relevant for this paper are as follows:

- *F8:P,E tally values for absorbed dose calculated with MCNPX nearest group boundary energy-indexing algorithm for electron transport agree within 0.3 % with the MCNP 6.3 default Landau straggling algorithm. However, the values are higher by up to 2 % compared to the MCNPX default bin-centered algorithm.
- *F8:P,E tally and F6:P tally values calculated by MCNPX 2.7.E differ by less than 0.8 % if the bin-centered algorithm is used for electron transport, or exceeds that value for $E \geq 10$ MeV and increases up to 1.5 % at $E = 30$ MeV if the nearest group boundary algorithm is used.
- F6:P tally in photon-only transport calculation results in the same value as in the coupled photon/electron transport calculation.
- F6:P tally and +F6 tally provide equivalent results.
- F6:P tallies calculated with MCNPX 2.7.E and MCNP 6.3 codes using the same cross section tables provide equivalent result.
- F4:P +DE/DF tally agrees with F6:P tally at lower energies but is lower for higher photon energies; the explanation is that this tally is defined in such a way that it is lacking radiative energy losses and counts collision energy losses only.
- F4:P +FM tally provides higher results than F6:P; the difference is even larger with respect to F4:P +DE/DF. However, this difference closely corresponds to $(1-g_a)$ values.

Therefore, for the calculations relevant for this paper, it is concluded that:

- It is not the aim of this paper to evaluate differences in electron energy-loss methods available in MCNP codes. It was decided that the dose calculation tallies in this Appendix would be compared to the “expected true value” of the absorbed dose obtained with the more recent electron transport algorithm available in the MCNPX code, which uses nearest group boundary method for calculation of electron energy losses.
- F6:P tally in photon-only transport calculation is a good estimate of the absorbed dose in tissue: the systematic uncertainty given by the difference between the absorbed dose obtained with the *F8-type tally and the kerma approximation of absorbed dose obtained

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3 955 with the F6:P-type tally is 0.05 % at 150 keV, 0.2 % at 662 keV, 0.5 % at 1.25 MeV, 0.8 %
4 956 at 10 MeV, 1.1 % at 20 MeV, and 1.5 % at 30 MeV under charged particle equilibrium.
5 957 • F4:P +FM is the total kerma.
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7 959 As a result, the F6:P tally in photon-only transport calculations was used to derive the absorbed
8 960 dose value in the phantoms and the F4:P tally with the FM multiplier (FM_{x-1 m-5-6}, x = tally number,
9 961 m = material number) was used to check the analytical determination of the total air kerma obtained
10 962 using equation (1).
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963 **Appendix C: Plots of conversion coefficients**

968 Figure C1: Values for $h'_K(0.07; E, \alpha)$ for various angles of radiation incidence, α , calculated in this study, h_{MC} , (red line),
 969 published in ISO 4037-3:2019, h_{ISO} , (blue crosses), and their relative difference, $RD = h_{MC}/h_{ISO} - 1$, at energies where values of
 970 both data sets were available (triangles, right axis).

975 Figure C2: Values for $h'_K(3; E, \alpha)$ for various angles of radiation incidence, α , calculated in this study, h_{MC} , (redline), published
 976 in ISO 4037-3:2019, h_{ISO} , (blue crosses), and their relative difference, $RD = h_{MC}/h_{ISO} - 1$, at energies where values of both data
 977 sets were available (triangles, right axis). ⁽¹⁾ Blue cross values for $E > 10$ MeV were taken from [54], Table A2, and corrected
 978 for $(1-g_a)$ values [50] used in the presented paper.

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981 Figure C3: Values for $h_K^*(10; E)$ calculated in this study, h_{MC} , (red line), published in ISO 4037-3:2019, h_{ISO} , (blue crosses),
 982 and their relative difference, $RD = h_{MC}/h_{ISO} - 1$, at energies where values of both data sets were available (triangles, right axis).

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986 Figure C4: Values for $h_{pK}(0.07; E)_{rod}$ for the rod phantom calculated in this study, h_{MC} , (red line), published in
 987 ISO 4037-3:2019, h_{ISO} , (blue crosses), and their relative difference, $RD = h_{MC}/h_{ISO} - 1$, at energies where values of both data sets
 988 were available (triangles, right axis).

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992 Figure C5: Values for $h_{pK}(0.07; E)_{pill}$ for the pillar phantom calculated in this study, h_{MC} , (red line), published in
 993 ISO 4037-3:2019, h_{ISO} , (blue crosses), and their relative difference, $RD = h_{MC}/h_{ISO} - 1$, at energies where values of both data sets
 994 were available (triangles, right axis).

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999 Figure C6: Values for $h_{pK}(0.07; E, \alpha)_{\text{slab}}$ for the slab phantom for various angles of radiation incidence, α , calculated in this
 1000 study, h_{MC} , (red line), published in ISO 4037-3:2019, h_{ISO} , (blue crosses), and their relative difference, $RD = h_{MC}/h_{ISO} - 1$, at
 1001 energies where values of both data sets were available (triangles, right axis).

Figure C7: Values for $h_{pK}(3; E, \alpha)_{cyl}$ for the cylinder phantom for various h angles of radiation incidence, α , calculated in this study, h_{MC} , (red line), published in ISO 4037-3:2019, h_{ISO} , (blue crosses), and their relative difference, $RD = h_{MC}/h_{ISO}-1$, at energies where values of both data sets were available (triangles, right axis).

Figure C8: Values for $h_{pK}(10; E, \alpha)_{\text{slab}}$ for the slab phantom for various angles of radiation incidence, α , calculated in this study, h_{MC} , (red line), published in ISO 4037-3:2019, h_{ISO} , (blue crosses), and their relative difference, $RD = h_{MC}/h_{ISO} - 1$, at energies where values of both data sets were available (triangles, right axis).

1015 **Appendix D: Tables of conversion coefficients**

1016 The tables are provided in the supplementary Excel file [71] only, because they are very large.

1017 Table D1: Conversion coefficients $h'_{\kappa}(0.07; E, \alpha)$ from total air kerma, K_a , to the directional dose equivalent $H'(0.07)$ for mono-
1018 energetic and parallel photon radiation (expanded and aligned field) as calculated in this study: see sheet “Table D1_H'(0.07)”
1019 in supplementary Excel file [71].

1020 Table D2: Conversion coefficients $h'_{\kappa}(3; E, \alpha)$ from total air kerma, K_a , to the directional dose equivalent $H'(3)$ for mono-
1021 energetic and parallel photon radiation (expanded and aligned field) as calculated in this study: see sheet “Table D2_H'(3)” in
1022 supplementary Excel file [71].

1023 Table D3: Conversion coefficients $h^*_{\kappa}(10; E)$ from total air kerma, K_a , to the ambient dose equivalent $H^*(10)$ for mono-
1024 energetic and parallel photon radiation (expanded and aligned field) as calculated in this study: see sheet “Table D3_Hamb(10)”
1025 in supplementary Excel file [71].

1026 Table D4: Conversion coefficients $h_{p\kappa}(0.07; E)_{\text{rod}}$ from total air kerma, K_a , to the dose equivalent $H_p(0.07)$ for mono-energetic
1027 and parallel photon radiation (expanded and aligned field) and the rod phantom at angle of radiation incidence of 0° as
1028 calculated in this study: see sheet “Table D4_Hp(0.07)rod” in supplementary Excel file [71].

1029 Table D5: Conversion coefficients $h_{p\kappa}(0.07; E)_{\text{pill}}$ from total air kerma, K_a , to the dose equivalent $H_p(0.07)$ for mono-energetic
1030 and parallel photon radiation (expanded and aligned field) and the pillar phantom at angle of radiation incidence of 0° as
1031 calculated in this study: see sheet “Table D5_Hp(0.07)pill” in supplementary Excel file [71].

1032 Table D6: Conversion coefficients $h_{p\kappa}(0.07; E, \alpha)_{\text{slab}}$ from total air kerma, K_a , to the dose equivalent $H_p(0.07)$ for mono-
1033 energetic and parallel photon radiation (expanded and aligned field) and the ICRU slab phantom as calculated in this study: see
1034 sheet “Table D6_Hp(0.07)slab” in supplementary Excel file [71].

1035 Table D7: Conversion coefficients $h_{p\kappa}(3; E, \alpha)_{\text{cyl}}$ from total air kerma, K_a , to the dose equivalent $H_p(3)$ for mono-energetic and
1036 parallel photon radiation (expanded and aligned field) and cylinder phantom consisting of ICRU tissue as calculated in this
1037 study: see sheet “Table D7_Hp(3)cyl” in supplementary Excel file [71].

1038 Table D8: Conversion coefficients $h_{p\kappa}(10; E, \alpha)_{\text{slab}}$ from total air kerma, K_a , to the dose equivalent $H_p(10)$ for mono-energetic
1039 and parallel photon radiation (expanded and aligned field) and the ICRU slab phantom as calculated in this study: see sheet
1040 “Table D8_Hp(10)slab” in supplementary Excel file [71].